

**THE CURRENT STATE OF VOCATIONAL GUIDANCE AND ITS
IMPLEMENTATION IN TEACHING THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE**

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Annotation: In this article, it is said on the issues of vocational guidance and its implementation in the secondary schools in the Fergana region.

Key words: vocational guidance, the content of English, learning materials, diagnostician, physical potential.

The professional and coherent duty of any promising schoolteacher is to educate schoolchildren in control of their education in accordance with science and technology development. In tandem with this, providing students with information about their target professions and implementing vocational guidance are also pedagogical tasks carried out directly in the course of this activity.

Vocational orientation in English lessons includes conducting diagnostician in order to find out the interests and the scientific and physical potential of the individuals, helping them to succeed in a particular profession and explaining it as a vital need for human beings. The reason for the fact that the implementation of these works have left a worthy place in the history of Uzbek pedagogy is that this problem is revealed as a philosophical "continual one," because the vocational orientation work has always been a problem of any time and space.

As has been stated in the document "International Action Plan on Aging Problems and United Nations Principles on Elderly" vocational guidance is a very crucial work for any shift in society. In these principles, The United Nations Organization highlighted that vocational guidance should be treated as a pedagogical problem in all countries and should be incorporated in the guidance as given in Recommendations

54-59 on occupational training and education which is important not only to improve the lives of young people but also the elderly.

In particular, it is stated in the following practical guidelines on vocational training and education: "In the preparation of policies and programs for information and vocational training, as well as the consequences of aging for development the need of the elder people should be taken into account. This issue applies to all ages, especially to the younger generation"

For this purpose, paragraph 54 of the Recommendation to the Member States is provided as follows. "Information and vocational training programs should have an international character, as the aging and retirement, the aged population will not only lead to a high degree of specialization but also make them mature in all respects. It is important to strengthen the management training level and sustain the different needs for aging".

The essence of the recommendation is to be understood by school teachers, and the issue of vocational guidance is to be accepted not only as a pedagogical problem but also as a starting point for solving political and economic problems. The role of foreign language teachers in these activities is particularly evident in the document that the issues of vocational training should be addressed internationally and should be based on their experiences with each other.

At the moment, the issue of directing schoolchildren to a particular profession is one of the issues which are being given special governmental attention in Uzbekistan.

As proof of our opinion, we can provide normative documents adopted by the Republic of Uzbekistan. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" was adopted on August 29, 1997, and the "National Training Program" aims to further improve the implementation of these tasks as well.

These documents required providing information for professional guidance in the content of the curriculum, including the use of the spiritual heritage of the Uzbek people and conducting the teaching process according to the democratic principles of education and implementation. Therefore, in the educational process, the legitimate

duty of each pedagogue is to use the heritage of our past scholars wisely and to convey their valuable ideas to the young generation thoroughly.

In order to make education more effective, it is also important to study the level of vocational orientation of young people in developed countries and to bring them as authentic material to schoolchildren. Here is an example of a questionnaire that reflects the relationships of young people towards fields and types of professions in Germany given in the newspaper “Markt”, volume 11, 2003. According to the given information in it 39,9 percent of students in the economy wanted to work in the field of entrepreneurship. The second-largest chosen field in this category is advertising. 62,3 percent of the students of applied informatics chose to be engaged in electronic data statistics. The second-largest number in the chosen field by these students is telecommunication. 54 percent of students of machinery were into work in the field of the car industry. The second-largest chosen field of these students is space technology. 37 percent of students in electronic sciences chose the field of telecommunication. The second largest part of them wanted to earn in the field of the car industry.

Data in the newspaper are presented as a result of surveys conducted by the German Goethe Institute staff. It gives statistical information on the areas which are chosen by German youth to work more in. As has been stated in it German students who are studying economics include the automobile industry, banking, service, finance, entrepreneurship; while students who were studying computer science had chosen the automobile industry, bank, aviation technology, and advertising industry. The students studying the automobile industry want to work in the field of chemicals, pharmaceuticals, energy, and environmental protection and those who are interested in electro-technical subjects would like to work in areas such as equipment, automobile industry, pyrotechnics, telecommunications, and environmental engineering.

Based on the information provided in the table, it is recommended that students should be exposed to conversations in the process of vocational guidance where they will be able to understand that they may work in different fields of occupation. While these studies give a few impressions of what qualities and abilities are required to

operate in a certain profession that they chose to work on and fasten the intention of the majority of students to occupy a particular profession. Thus, the emphasis on pupils' attention to the particular aspects of the profession during the learning process will further strengthen their enthusiasm for the occupation.

The results of a survey conducted in Fergana in Uzbekistan in 2022 has shown that a significant number of students who are learning in 7-9th grade in secondary schools chose to work in the field of education, medicine, and tourism. The fields of the car industry, administration, transport, press, and telecommunication have been chosen the least. One of the students could not choose any field. 56 percent of students wanted to work with people while 18 percent of them chose to work with technologies. The fields of human nature and human signs were chosen by 10 percent of pupils. These numbers assign us to make our pupils motivate to these kinds of fields because the issues of using digital technologies and environment are ever increasing in today's world. This trend requires exposing pupils to choose these kinds of professions.

Table 1

Fields	Types of field	Number	Percent
Not chosen		1	1, 3
Art	Human-artistic image	3	3, 9
Tourism	Human-nature	8	10
Bank	Human-signs	4	5, 2
Design	Human-signs	3	3, 9
Press	Human-signs	1	1, 3
Military	Human-technics	9	12
The car industry	Human-technic	1	1, 3
Electricity	Human-technics	2	2, 6
Transport	Human-technics	1	1, 3
Telecommunication	Human-technic	1	1, 3
Sport	Human-human	2	2, 6
Business	Human-human	3	3, 9
Internal affairs	Human-human	2	2, 6
Administration	Human-human	1	1, 3
Education	Human-human	13	17
Law	Human-human	5	6, 5
Service	Human-human	5	6, 5
Medicine	Human-human	9	12
Commerce	Human-human	3	3, 9

lyceum, and school after graduating the school. Some pupils go back to study at school after they begin to study at vocational colleges or lyceums.

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